
UNVEILING THE POTENTIALS OF CHICKPEA IN ZIMBABWE- A REVIEW

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Abstract:

Biophysical constraints such as soil infertility and erratic rainfall patterns negatively impact crop production and productivity and threaten to further worsen food and nutrition insecurity and environmental vulnerability. Therefore, the integration of legumes for diversification of cropping systems, currently dominated by maize mono-crops, has the potential to increase resilience. Traditional legume options for diversification, which include groundnut and common bean, have limited resilience against climate change variability. Hence, a need to introduce other new legume crops that are proving to be efficient in other countries like chickpeas. Chickpea is reported to thrive well in semi-arid conditions, with the capacity to reclaim degraded soils due to its nitrogen-fixing ability, and can help fight hidden hunger amongst the poor-resourced communities who solely depend on agriculture production for sustainable livelihoods. Therefore, a review was carried out to unveil the hidden potentials and opportunities for the adoption and utilization of the crop in sub-Saharan Africa to reduce malnutrition and improve soil fertility which in both terms sustains food and nutrition security of smallholder farmers in semi-arid regions where production of cereal crops like maize is now a challenge.

Keywords: Chickpea, utilization, potentials, food security.

Introduction:

Agricultural production faces a fundamental challenge of climate change and variability which is mainly characterized by erratic rainfall, extreme temperatures, and pest and disease incidences (Thornton et.al, 2015; Serdeczny et.al, 2017). Climate change and variability coupled with poor degraded soil have undermined crop production capacity and threatened food security in smallholder farming systems of sub-Saharan Africa (FAO 2012; Gizaw 2017). In the wake of the ever-increasing challenges on food security, nations are trying to revitalize and diversify the agricultural sector by adopting and promoting underutilized and orphaned crops such as chickpeas that can be grown successfully under the current climatic conditions. According to (Phiri et al., 2023), chickpea is perceived to be the panacea for reclaiming degraded soils, addressing micronutrient deficient, and enhancing food and nutrition security among resource-limited smallholder farmers.

Endowed with the advantages of efficient utilization of available limited soil moisture and nutrients, deep tap roots and the capacity to reclaim degraded soils chickpea is a good option for a sustainable crop production system (Fikre et al 2020). The crop is drought tolerant, due to its deep tap root system which allows the crop to extract water from deeper layers in the soil profile (Hussen 2015). According to (ICAR, 2022.), chickpea can grow on residual moisture which allows farmers to engage in double cropping, where chickpea is sown at the end of the rainy season following the harvest of the main crop (Kauthekar et al., 2016). This permits more intensive and productive land use, particularly in areas where land is scarce. The crop plays an important role in improving soil structure and fertility by fixing atmospheric nitrogen; where it is reported to meet 80% of its nitrogen (N) requirement (Sarraf et al., 1998). The crop leaves a substantial amount of residual nitrogen for subsequent crops and adds organic matter to maintain and improve soil health and fertility, which in turn lessens the burden of buying synthetic fertilizers on resource-limited farmers (Kamran Taj et al., 2020).

The crop is a very versatile pulse with a large seed size that contains essential nutrients that are key for human development especially in developing nations where malnutrition is common (Kamran Taj et al 2020). It contains about 22% protein, 27% carbohydrates, 3% fat, β -carotene $0.5 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, folates $405 - 537 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (Jukanti et al., 2012a; Parwada et al., 2023). Apart from nutritional benefits to humans, chickpea crop residue is rich in digestible crude protein content compared with other legume crops which makes it ideal for animal feed (Jukanti et al., 2012b; Yadav et al. 2017).

Despite all the plethora of benefits outlined, chickpea is one of the underutilized pulse crops in Zimbabwe and its production is substantially low as compared to other African countries. Reasons for low production range from the unavailability of improved varieties, farmers' preferences, knowledge gaps in crop husbandry practices, and unavailability of market links (Charachimwe et al., 2023; Parwada et al., 2023 ; Mthulisi et al., 2020). Furthermore, the crop is not a traditional crop in Zimbabwe which requires the government, research and extension system, and different stakeholders to promote uptake (Mthulisi & Mcebisi, 2020; Parwada et al., 2023). Therefore, it is against this background that a review was carried out to unveil the hidden potential and opportunities for the adoption and use of chickpea.

Origin and Botany:

There is a debate among authors regarding the origin of chickpea. In the opinion of De Candolle (1882), chickpea is reported to have originated in the regions between Greece and the Himalayas, while Vavilov (1926) considered South-West Asia and the Mediterranean as

the probable centres of origin of the crop. He also proposed that Ethiopia could be the secondary centre or origin while Harlan (1969), agrees that Ethiopia is the centre of diversity of chickpea (Vishnyakova et al., 2017). However, earlier research from different authors qualifies modern-day South-Eastern Turkey and Northern Syria to be the true origins of the crop since other closely related wild species are found there (Van der Maesen 1987; Anonymous, 1974; Gaur et al., 2010; Pratap, 2011; Kerem et al., 2007).

The cultivated chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*) is an ancient legume that belongs to the Fabaceae family and its cultivation started about 7000 years ago (Singh, 1995). Consequently, the crop has spread widely across 57 countries distributed in Asia, Europe, South America, and some parts of Africa (Ladizinsky, 1975; FAO, 2002; Hussena et al., 2015). The crop has several names depending on the region, in Spanish it is called 'garbanzo', in French 'pois chiche', in German 'kicher', in Hindi 'chana' in English 'gram or Bengal gram' and in Russia and Turkey the crop is called 'nakhut' (Aries van der Maesen, 1987; Singh, 1995; Corp et al., 2004; Akibode et al., 2011).

Chickpea is the nineteenth most important crop grown all over the world and is ranked second among pulses and other legumes. According to the FAO database global chickpea production has increased by 2.6% between 2015 and 2020 with India contributing 80% of the global production followed by Turkey, Russia, Myanmar, and Pakistan (FAOSTAT, 2020). In Africa, Ethiopia is ranked the 1st as it is the largest producer contributing 4% of the global market (FAOSTAT, 2020).

Chickpea is an annual herbaceous legume with plant height ranging from 30-70cm. The plant generally produces diffused primary, secondary, and tertiary spreading branches covered with glandular hairs resembling a small bush. Based on shape and size, cultivated chickpea have been grouped into two types; the Desi (microsperma) and the Kabuli (macrosperma) (Cubero 1975; Singh et al. 1995). Desi chickpea is adapted to winter cropping in the hilly areas of the subtropics and tropics whilst the kabuli is mainly established in spring at higher altitudes.

Desi: Accounts for 80%-85% of the world's production and is well known for its small seeds that are light brown to dark with rough pigmented seed coats ranging from brown, yellow, green to black. Desi is a short-erect and drought-tolerant type that originated from India and is characterised by small leaflets and purplish flowers (Gaur et al. 2015).

Kabuli: This type is characterised by large cream or beige colored and 'ram's head' seeds with white flowers. It is found in higher rainfall areas and is a late maturing type that is taller when compared with Desi and is mostly favoured on the market (Moreno and Cubero 1978; Upadhyaya et al. 2008).

Chickpea plants have a robust taproot system that can penetrate up to 1.5- 2 m deep. It also has 3 to 4 rows of lateral roots that are rich in starch and bear rhizobium nodules. These nodules allow the crop to fix soil nitrogen through symbiotic relationships with the bacteria. Chickpea can fix more nitrogen (about 80%) when compared with other pulse and legume crops (Cubero 1987; Corby 1981).

Chickpea stems are erect, branched, spreading, hairy, viscous green and sometimes shrubby, which can grow up to 1m. The stem has a natural way of protecting the plant against insectpest by secreting a highly acidic substance that contains malic, oxalic, and citric acids (Singh & Diwakar, 2020). Generally, the plant has primary branches that range from 1-8 which are thick and strong which arise from ground level. It also has 2-12 secondary branches which develop at buds that are located on the primary branches which makes them

less vigorous as compared to primary branches. Secondary branches have a bearing factor on yield as they determine the total number of leaves and leaf index area. The major growth habits are derived from the branch angle which ranges from erect (0-15), semi-erect (16-25), semi-spreading (26-60), spreading (61-80), and prostrate with branches flat on the ground (Iv et al., 2013).

Generally, chickpea have three types of leaves the normal which is uni-imparipinnate, Simple which has the leaf lamina not differentiated into leaflets and ranches and the multipennate with the leaf lamina which is differentiated more than once. The number of leaflets ranges from 5-17 which can be pale green and light purple that are pubescent depending on the type. The serrated leaflets are ovate to elliptic with the base cuneate or rounded in shape and their length ranging from 6-20mm long and 5-14mm wide (Singh & Diwakar, 1995). The two types of chickpeas can be easily differentiated by the colour of their flowers, Desi has purple or violet flowers while Kabuli has white flowers. The hairy flowers are solitary and have an intermediate growth habit where they continue to flower and set pods as long as conditions are favourable (Singh & Diwakar, 1995). Pod setting normally occurs on primary and secondary branches which are short, inflated, and pubescent with a unique spherical shape that looks like a thorn. The number of pods per plant ranges from 30-150 depending on the genotype. Usually, the Desi type sets 2 dark seeds per pod that are angular shaped while the Kabuli sets one rounded seed per pod which is pale cream (Singh & Diwakar, 1987; Van Der Maesen, 1995.)

Chickpea germplasm:

Worldwide, it is estimated that 80,000 accessions of chickpea collections which include landraces, breeding material, and wild species have been conserved in 30 gene banks (Vishnyakova et al., 2017). The genus *Cicer* comprises about 42 wild species and yet a single cultivated species *Cicer arietinum* L (Dixit, 2022; Ohri & Pal, 1991; Singh & Diwakar, 2020). The ICRISAT genebank holds 308 accessions belonging to 18 species of wild *Cicer* from 14 countries but the majority of these wild relatives (34) are perennials while a few (8) are annuals (Choumane and Baum, 2000). The cultivated species is an annual crop. The general grouping of the members of the *Cicer* genera has been proposed as follows:

- (a) The primary genepool (GP1): this is composed of one cultivated species *C. arietinum* and two wild species i.e., *C. echinospermum* (P.H. Davis) and *C. reticulatum* (Ladiz.) (Ladizinsky and Adler, 1976). Some authors also group the perennial wild *Cicer* species *C. anatolicum* Alef., with the primary genepool species (Choumane and Baum, 2000).
- (b) The secondary genepool (GP2): made up of three wild *Cicer* species i.e., *C. judaicum* (Boiss.), *C. pinnatifidum* (Jaub). and Spach (Tayyar and Waines, 1996).
- (c) The tertiary genepool (GP3): includes three annuals wild *Cicer* species, *C. yamashitae* (Kitam.), *C. chorassanicum* (Bunge) Popov and *C. cuneatum* (Hochst. ex A. Rich.), (Ahmad et al, 2005).

The secondary gene pool is closely related to the primary gene pool while the tertiary is distantly related to the former. Earlier work by Ladizinsky and Adler (1976) explored gene transferability between cultivated and wild species with some positive results obtained. Of the crossable groups, the resultant interspecific hybrids had variable fertility as some crosses yielded non-viable seeds. Gene transfer between the wild species to the cultivated species was possible for *C. reticulatum*, a wild progenitor of the cultivated species, and *C. echinospermum*, a member of the secondary gene pool.

Globally the most significant collections, estimated at 86500 accessions, are deposited in gene banks at the International Crop Research Institute of the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT),

Hyderabad; International Centre for Agricultural Research for Dry Areas (ICARDA), Syria; National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources (NBPGR), India and at other gene banks countries such as Australia, Iran and the USA (Verma et al., 2015). Access to germplasm is governed by international laws on sharing genetic wealth. In southern Africa, ICRISAT is the main known source of germplasm in countries such as Malawi, Ethiopia, and Zimbabwe (Ohri & Pal, 1991). Zimbabwe being a signatory to the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture which came into effect in 2004 has benefited from accessing the chickpea lines through the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT, 2020). According to the Department of Research Technical report of (2020), the department is working in collaboration with ICRISAT on the adaptability of four Kabuli lines four Desi lines in a quest to avail improved chickpea varieties on the market for adoption, production, and utilization.

General requirements:

Climate

The crop can be grown on a wide variation of agro-climate conditions depending on the region. According to Smithson et al. 1985; Singh & Diwakar, 1995), the crop is being grown between 20°N and 40°N in the northern hemisphere and at relatively higher elevations in India and Ethiopia between an elevation of 10°N and 20°N. These differences in longitude and altitude also translate to different temperatures, precipitation, and photoperiod which then alter the time of sowing from one region to another. In general, the crop is a cool season crop that is being grown as a winter crop in the tropics, as a summer or spring crop in temperate environments, and as a dry climate crop in semi-arid (Singh & Diwakar, 1995; Van Der Maesen, 1987; Vishnyakova et al., 2017). Although chickpea is considered a crop of temperate regions that is grown in winter, its cultivation is gradually spreading to sub-tropical and tropical regions of Asia, Africa and North America where it is cultivated on a large scale in arid and semiarid environments in summer (Gowda et al. 2009; Mohammed et al 2016). The crop thrives in temperatures between 18 °C to 29 °C and annual rainfall of about 400 mm to 600 mm (Madzivhandila et al., 2012; Parwada et al., 2023), making it ideal for production in summer in the temperate regions and in winter or early spring in the Sub-tropic regions of Zimbabwe. Moreover, its ability to perform better under low rainfall conditions renders it a potential crop for production in the semi-arid regions of the country where low rainfall is received.

Supporting the introduction of the crop in the subtropic regions of Sub- Sahara Africa, (Madzivhandila et al., 2012), conducted research in the summer to evaluate the growth, performance, and yield of chickpea in South Africa, and results showed enhanced grain yield in chickpea grown in the summer season with the application of 45 and 90 kg P/ha. These results are comparable to the findings of (Parwada et al., 2023), in Zimbabwe proving the potential to introduce the crop in Zimbabwe in areas where the temperatures are below 32°C. Production of chickpea in such areas can not only ensure suitable temperatures but also moisture from the summer rainfall since most farmers depend on rainfed crop production.

Soils:

There is a discord amongst authors in terms of ideal soils for optimum yields of chickpea. According to Virender et. al (2004), chickpeas grow well on heavy black or red soils with a pH range of 6-7, whilst Singh et al (1995), posit that the crop performs well on silt loam soils with good drainage agreed with Moolani and Chandra (1970), who also reported that deep loam or silty clay soils are ideal. (Mahler et al. 1988), also indicated that in Pakistan and

India, chickpea is grown successfully on sand to sandy loam soils with a pH range of 5.7 to 7.2. While other authors ascribe that in Central India, West Asia, and in the Ethiopian highlands the crop thrives well in deep black calciferous with a soil pH between 6.0 to 9.0 (Kumar et al., 2006; Ebessa, 2002). This divergence in schools of thought has confused our farmers who depend on indigenous knowledge and literature from other countries which has led them not to venture into chickpea production. Therefore, there is a need to carry out experiments on different soil types in Zimbabwe to come up with authentic recommendations for farmers.

However, background literature indicates that the crop requires fertile, sandy-loam soil with good internal drainage with a pH range of 6 to 7 and do not tolerate water-logged conditions and is highly sensitive to salinity (Chandra 1980; Fikre et al., 2020; Azeem et al., 2019). Salinity adversely affects dry matter production and up-take of essential nutrients such as phosphorus, zinc, and iron by roots which in turn impacts yield (Dravid and Goswami 1987; Mahler et al. 1988). Therefore, drawing from the findings of Nyamapfene who contacted a geographical overview of the Zimbabwean soils and their Agricultural Potential, chickpea can be a potential crop in Zimbabwe. According to Nyamapfene 66% of the area of this country is covered by crystalline rocks, of which granites are by far the most predominant. As a result, soils of granitic origin which are sand soils cover 46% of the country (Nyamapfene, 1992), hence chickpea can be potentially grown in the country since it thrives well in sandy soils.

Fertiliser and Nutritional Requirements:

The current approach to fertiliser use is based on laboratory nutrient analysis of soil; however, some general recommendations have been suggested regardless of area and analysis. These generalised recommendations vary widely across authors. The nitrogen requirements of chickpeas are not well understood because it is believed that the crop obtains its nitrogen through nitrogen fixation. Saxena and Yadav (1975), noted that for sand soils it is ideal to apply 15-25 kg N/ha in sand soils which is in agreement with Patel and Patel (1991), who propounded that 20 kg N/ha is ideal for sandy loam soils. Rajendran et al. (1982), also noted that 30-40 kg N/ha is the best for chickpea in India. The general recommendations of ICRISAT say that 20-30 kg N/ha is ideal. However, some authors believe high N can inhibit nodulation and crop nitrogen fixation and therefore should be applied only if the soil analysis suggested it to be applied.

Phosphorus is a major nutrient element for high and sustained productivity of grain legumes such as chickpea which is essential for general health, vigorous root development and increasing nitrogen-fixing capacity of the crop (Hussen, 2015). But however, like any other nutrients, there are varying recommendations across the globe amongst different authors who proposed 22kg, 32kg, 35kg of P in Syria, India, and Ethiopia respectively (Saxena and Sheldrake, 1980; Singh et al., 1981; Saxena, 1984). McKay (2002), reiterated that P can be safely applied in the seed row up to rates that are used for wheat because it requires more P to increase the nitrogen-fixing rate and capacity. In general, 40–60 kg P ha⁻¹ are recommended, figures slightly higher than other crops' requirements. There is limited information on potassium (K) but its application rate should be based on nutrient analysis of soil. On soils from a parent material with high K content, higher levels of available K will be a waste of resources. Depending on the soil analysis, low K soils require further fertiliser management practices to avoid losses through leaching. However, there are variations in the information available in the literature where Saxena and Yadav (1975); Hamidullah et al. (1989),

recommended 17-50 kg K/ha in Asia against a generalised recommendation of 17 to 25 kg K ha⁻¹.

Soil degradation has taken a huge toll on the plant's available micronutrients and major losses occur through the erosion of topsoil. There is ample evidence pointing to yield benefits where micronutrients were applied to chickpeas. A combination of Boron (B) and Molybdenum (Mo) significantly improved yields in an experiment where other macro- and secondary nutrients were supplied (Shil et al., 2007). It is clear from available research results that there is discord when it comes to ideal fertiliser recommendations for chickpea production in smallholder farms. More work is required to arrive at sustainable macronutrients (K and P) and micronutrients (B, Mo and Zn). Site-specific nutrient management in cereal crops has already paved the way for generating balanced, efficient and economical local recommendations (Singh et al., 2015). Sustainable nutrient rates will motivate most farmers to adopt the chickpea leading to increased production and productivity.

Chickpea contributes to the soil-N budget through biological nitrogen fixation (BNF). Previous work suggests that the crop has the potential to meet about 80% of the internal N requirements through BNF. Giller (2001) reported that the amount of N fixed ranges up to 124 kg N ha⁻¹ under favourable growing conditions. However, symbiosis results are responsive to local soil and climatic conditions. The inoculant suitability, inoculation efficiency, opportunities for coreinoculation and related P management need to be explored for chickpea. Work of Barriuso et al. (2008) has shown the usefulness of a combination of microsymbionts in increasing nutrient and water use efficiencies.

Markets and Economics:

Literature indicates that the global production of chickpeas has increased by 2.6% between 2015 and 2020 with, India being the biggest contributor to the world market (FAOSTATS 2021). In Africa, only Ethiopia, Tanzania, Burkina Faso and Ghana are contributing significantly, leaving a wide gap for other countries to penetrate the market systems (Mthulisi et. al, 2020). The crop is being exported to over 50 countries which include Bangladesh, the United Arab Emirates, Spain, Algeria, Turkey and Italy (Muehlbauer et.al, 2017). On the other hand, the world consumption of chickpeas has also been increasing in recent years, due to the rampant population growth and health issues. Most countries have adopted the crop to be used in school feeding programs since it is a good source of plant-based protein and other essential nutrients suitable for children below the age of five (Fikre et.al, 2020). Hence, the demand for the crop across the globe has drastically increased, and those countries producing the crop are failing to satisfy the market creating more opportunities for chickpea production in other countries like Zimbabwe (Merga 2019). However, some challenges need to be addressed to increase chickpea production in Zimbabwe, such as lack of access to inputs and markets, poor infrastructure, and limited access to extension service.

Potential of chickpeain Zimbabwe:

Chickpea is grown in arid to semiarid conditions. Though extreme weather conditions do not support higher yields in chickpeas, cool environments with moderate to high rainfall have been used for production. Under these conditions, both biotic and abiotic factors influence the yield potential of the crop (Cacho et al. 2020). Jha et al. (2014), identified three climatic parameters for future consideration in the chickpea improvement programs i.e., drought, heat and cold stress. Given the climate scenarios in the recent past, Zimbabwe has experienced extremes associated with the disruption of seasonal rainfall and temperature patterns

(Mamombe et.al, 2011), as such chickpea varieties with tolerance to extreme weather conditions would be required. In addition, a suite of other climate-smart technologies (Nhamo et. al, 2017) need to be explored in defining the potential for chickpea in new growing areas. Multiple strategy approaches of targeting varieties that exhibit escape, avoidance, and tolerance need to be taken to increase diversity.

Chickpea is a nutrient-dense pulse crop with diverse nutrients that are essential for fighting hidden hunger and malnutrition deficiencies (Wang 2021). Malnutrition is still a challenge in Zimbabwe and other southern African countries and therefore, the production and consumption of protein-dense crops have been recommended (Mthulisi 2020). Physiological adaptation characteristics to note include the rhizo-symbiotic ability of chickpeas which has important positive implications on both nutrient and water abstraction from soils. Furthermore, the crop can be used as an alternative animal feed because it is rich in digestible crude protein (Yadav et al. 2017).

Research gaps:

Extreme weather and variability threaten the crop diversification initiative on various crops. With the advent of modern molecular breeding techniques, which are gene and loci-targeted, improved chickpea varieties can be developed to suit the evolving environments. With these approaches, more environment and gene pool-specific management practices aimed at reducing the impact of extreme weather conditions on productivity need to be explored. Both screening for adaptation to climatic variability and resource use efficiency agronomic experiments are urgently required in Zimbabwe. Wide varietal adaptation could be an important trait given the climate variability and change associated with the target environments. High resource use efficiency i.e., nutrient-, water- and radiation-use-efficiency have been lauded as important mechanisms of ensuring increased productivity and production. However, despite the experimental evidence on the importance of these efficiencies, only a few agronomic guidance have been developed into user-friendly tools for practical application on smallholder farmers. More validation working on combining the multiple use-efficiencies at the farm level is required to equip farmers with management skills.

Conclusions and Recommendations:

The development of suitable chickpea varieties adapted to the Zimbabwean climate contributes to an improved basket of diverse crop combinations for both food and nutrition purposes in smallholder farming communities. Chickpea, a nutrient-dense crop, has the potential to improve livelihood in smallholder farming communities in Zimbabwe. Similarly, its large markets can also improve incomes for new farmers in a range of environmental conditions. Adaptive research on agronomic practices, varietal suitability, post-harvest value addition, and storage are key knowledge needs for smallholder farmers.

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